

SoildiverAgro project

Adoption of new management practices to increase crop production and quality

THE WHAT AND WHY

Recommendations for the use of biostimulants in wheat cultivation in the continental region

High infestation rates with soil-borne and mycotoxin-producing plant pathogenic fungi such as *Fusarium* are posing challenges for wheat cultivation in the continental region. Infestation reduces yield levels and, due to mycotoxin contamination, also yield quality. Currently, fungicides are being used on a large scale as a preventive measure, which, however, can negatively impact soil health or lead to resistances. Thus, alternatives are required in the long term. In this context, bioregulation by fungivorous soil animals (especially collembolans and mites) represents a promising approach, as these act as antagonists and can reduce fungi and mycotoxin contamination of plant material. Against this background, the identification of management adaptations that enable fungicide reduction and at the same time promote bioregulation through antagonists is of great relevance. In a

case study, the extent to which the application of a biostimulant in combination with a plant adjuvant under fungicide reduction contributes to the strengthening of soil self-regulation and the control of *Fusarium* was investigated. Based on the results of this study, promoting the use of biostimulants in combination with plant adjuvants in wheat cultivation is recommended in order to increase the diversity of collembolans, promote the ecosystem services they provide and reduce fungal pathogens. From an agro-ecological perspective, this measure has the potential to promote soil biodiversity, improve plant and soil health, and to compensate for a reduction in fungicide use. From an agro-economic point of view, however, no effects on crop revenue are to be expected based on the results available so far.

1. Wheat cultivation under application of a biostimulant in combination with a plant adjuvant in the case study.

KEYWORDS

Wheat cultivation, biostimulant, bioregulation, plant pathogenic fungi, soil fauna

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